

3,4-Bond Cleavage of Tetrahydro- β -Carboline Alkaloids : Transformation of Venenatine and Rhazine to the Corresponding 2-Acylindole Derivatives

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3,4-Bond cleavage reactions of venenatine (1) and rhazine (6) with cyanogen bromide in ethanolic chloroform were studied. The resulting seco-bases were transformed to the corresponding 2-acylindoles with *t*-BuOCl.

MANY 2-acylindole alkaloids are known to co-occur with tetrahydro- β -carboline bases in plants^{1,2}. Hence it is reasonable to suppose that these 2-acylindoles are biogenetically derived from the corresponding tetrahydro- β -carboline bases by a reaction sequence the key step of which involves a 3,4-bond cleavage with subsequent oxidation at C-3. Though definite evidence involving *in vivo* experiments with radio-labelled compounds is lacking, laboratory analogies³⁻⁸ for this transformation are known. We have been interested for some time in this type of transformation⁹ and in the present paper we report the results of our studies on the 3,4-bond cleavage reaction of venenatine⁹ (1), an yohimbine alkaloid of *Alstonia venenata*, and rhazine^{10,11} (6), a sarpagine-type base of *Rhazya stricta*, with the intension of converting these to the corresponding 2-acylindoles.

Results and Discussion

Transformation of venenatine (1): Venenatine (1) was converted to its 2-acylindole derivative in three steps as shown in Scheme I. The 3,4-bond cleavage in venenatine was brought about by treatment with CNBr in EtOH-CHCl₃ in the first step, when two products (2a and 2b) were obtained. The structures of 2a and 2b were settled on the basis of detailed spectroscopic studies and chemical reactions. The mass spectra of these compounds exhibited molecular ion peaks at *m/e* 455 corresponding to the molecular formula C₂₅H₃₃N₃O₅, having additional -CN and -OCH₂CH₃ groups to venenatine. In addition to the MS, the other spectral data (uv, ir, ¹H- and ¹³C-nmr) of 2a and 2b confirmed their structures to be 3-ethoxy-3,4-seco-cyanamide of venenatine (1). The ¹H-nmr spectra of 2a and 2b showed the presence of ethoxy protons and the expected shift of the C-3-H to δ 4.66 and δ 4.10 respectively, from that of venenatine (at δ 4.45)⁹. The stereochemistry at C-3 was settled on the basis of stereospecific ring closure reactions of 2a and 2b with glacial acetic acid at 70° to venenatine (1) and alstovenine (5) respectively⁹. Both ring closures furnished exclusively one product. The

ring closures occurred by an acid-catalysed direct S_N2 displacement of the ethoxy groups. Hence it was confirmed that 2a was 3S and 2b the 3R-compound. Sakai *et al*⁸ had earlier made similar stereochemical assignments for the 3-ethoxy-3,4-seco-cyanamides of yohimbine and hirsutine.

The 20 MHz ¹³C-nmr spectra of 2a and 2b were studied in CDCl₃. The assignment of the ¹³C-shifts of these compounds have been made on the basis of the comparison of the δ values with those of venenatine¹¹ and also on the basis of SFORD multiplicities. The assignments are shown in Scheme II. Characteristic new signals were discernible for the cyano and the ethoxy carbons in the spectra of 2a and 2b. Moreover, the C-3 showed the expected downfield shift of *ca* 20 ppm in the seco-products with respect to that of venenatine (venenatine C-3 appears at 53.8 ppm)¹¹. The chemical shifts of this carbon, however, differed by 3.7 ppm for the diastereoisomeric 2a and 2b. An interesting observation was that C-12 had shifted upfield by *ca* 6 ppm in the seco products in comparison with that of venenatine (venenatine C-12 appears at 105.7 ppm)¹¹.

The next step (Scheme I) was the formation of the 3-keto-3,4-seco-cyanamide derivative (3) from the 3-ethoxy derivatives, 2a and 2b. A mixture of 2a and 2b was treated with Pb(OAc)₄ in glacial AcOH at room temperature to give a complex mixture of products from which 3 was isolated in low yield by preparative tlc. However, the yield could be dramatically improved when the oxidation was carried out with *t*-BuOCl. In this case 3 was obtained in 85% yield on subsequent warming with water in presence of traces of acid. The uv spectrum of 3 exhibited absorption maxima [311, 249 and 206 nm (log ϵ : 2.93, 3.08 and 3.26)] characteristic of 2-acylindoles, the presence of which moiety was further substantiated by the appearance of an ir band at 1710 cm⁻¹ (α,β -unsaturated >C=O). The absence of ethoxy protons and the C-3-H in ¹H-nmr spectrum and the absence of the ethoxy carbons and appearance of a downfield signal (τ 193.1 ppm,

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Reagents : (i) CNBr in EtOH-CHCl₃ (1 : 3), excess Na₂CO₃, r.t., 48 hr (ii) Pb(OAc)₂ in glacial AcOH, r.t., 5 hr
 (iii) *t*-BuOCl/NEt₃ in CH₂Cl₂ and CCl₄, 0°, stirred (iv) 1% AcOH in 70% MeOH-H₂O, 70°, N₂, 3 hr
 (v) 5 mole equivalent of NH₄OAc in 5% H₂O-AcOH, 70°, N₂, 8 hr.

Scheme I. Conversion of 1 to 4.

assigned to C-3 carbonyl) in the ¹³C-nmr spectrum also confirmed the structural assignment as 3.

In the final step, conversion of 3 to 4 (Scheme I) was achieved by treating the former with 5 mole equivalent of NH₄OAc in glacial AcOH. 4, C₂₁H₂₅N₂O₅ (M⁺ 386), was obtained in rather poor yield (ca 10%). The N-decyanation was accompanied by hydrolysis of the ester group. As this process of conversion of N-CN to N-H, originally adopted by Sakai *et al*⁸, was not very satisfactory, we attempted to effect the same conversion by passing HCl gas into a methanolic solution of the alkaloid and subsequent hydrolysis. However, this did not result in any significant improvement of the yield. The ir spectrum (KBr) of the product 4 showed the absence of any band around 2200 cm⁻¹.

(for -CN), but a broad hydroxyl band appeared at 3400-3200 cm⁻¹.

Transformation of rhazine (6) : Conversion of rhazine (6) into its 2-acyl derivative (7) was achieved in two steps (Scheme III). Due to paucity of the material, further studies in this series could not be made. Rhazine (6) was treated with cyanogen bromide under the same conditions employed in case of venenatine (Scheme I). Two products (6a and 6b) were isolated and their structures were settled to be 3-ethoxy-3,4-seco-cyanamide derivative of rhazine, on the basis of detailed spectroscopic studies (uv, ir, MS, ¹H- and ¹³C-nmr). The stereochemistry at C-3 could not be determined by stereospecific ring closure reaction with glacial acetic acid as in the case of venenatine, since the reaction with

Scheme II. ^{13}C -shift (in ppm) assignment of 2a, 2b and 3.

glacial acetic acid led to a complex mixture of products which included unreacted starting materials in large amount. A tentative suggestion regarding the stereochemistry has been made from analogy. Venenatine (1) under the same solvolytic conditions of the cleavage reaction afforded predominantly the C-3 inversion product. Hence, it may be suggested that 6a, the major product, was the "3R" compound, as the starting material, rhazine (6), has a "3S" configuration. Since 6a and 6b are epimeric at C-3, 6b would therefore presumably be the 3S compound.

The 20 MHz ^{13}C -nmr spectra of 6a and 6b were studied in CDCl_3 . These were in agreement with the proposed seco-structures. The assignments of the carbon signals of these compounds have been made on the basis of comparison of the chemical shifts of vobasinol¹² (8), multiplicities of the signals in the SFORD spectra and intercomparisons (Scheme IV). The C-3 carbon showed a downfield shift of ca 6.2 ppm in the seco-products (6a and 6b) with respect to that of vobasinol (8)¹² (vobasinol C-3 appears at 66.8 ppm) presumably due to the α -effect caused by the O-alkyl substituent.

In the next step (Scheme III) the seco products (6a and 6b) were converted to 3-keto-3,4-seco-cyanamide derivative (7) by treatment with *t*-BuOCl. 7 exhibited uv absorption maxima typical of 2-acylindole. It showed the absence of C-3-H and the ethoxy protons in the ^1H -nmr spectrum and the appearance of an ir band at 1705 cm^{-1} for α,β -unsaturated carbonyl in addition to the other expected bands. All these data point to the 3-keto-3,4-seco-cyanamide structure for 7. One point needs mention in this connection is that in the ^1H -nmr the ester methyl resonated at δ 3.73 instead of resonating at ca δ 2.50, a characteristic value for the sarpagine-type alkaloids and the corresponding 3-ethoxy-3,4-seco derivatives. This indicated a conformational change of the 10-membered ring (previously rings C and D), so that the carbomethoxyl group was no longer situated in the shielding region of the aromatic nucleus.

Experimental

Melting points were recorded on an electrically heated Kofler Block and are uncorrected. The uv spectra were recorded on a Varian 634S spectrophotometer in 95% aldehyde-free ethanol. The ir spectra were recorded in KBr disc on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer and the rotations measured on a Perkin-Elmer 241 polarimeter. The ^1H - and ^{13}C -nmr spectra were recorded on Varian CFT-20 NMR spectrometer in CDCl_3 using TMS as internal standard. Brockman alumina (basic) (B.D.H.) was used for column chromatography; silica gel G (Gouri Chemicals, Calcutta) and alumina G (B.D.H.) were used for thin layer chromatography. Reactions were carried out with authentic samples of rhazine and venenatine isolated earlier in our laboratory.

Preparation of 2a and 2b: CNBr (424 mg; 4 mmole) was added with stirring to a solution of venenatine (1) (382 mg; 1 mmole) in dry EtOH- CHCl_3 (1 : 3) (100 ml). Anhydrous Na_2CO_3 (1.0 g) was added and the reaction mixture kept for 48 hr at room temperature. It was then filtered and the filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure. The two products 2a (R_f 0.50) and 2b (R_f 0.60) were isolated by ptlc on alumina chromatoplates using EtOAc as the developing solvent. Overall isolated yield of the seco-products was 85% (2a, 60%; 2b, 25%). 2a (275 mg; 60%) was isolated as a yellow solid, $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{33}\text{N}_3\text{O}_5$, m.p. $204\text{--}205^\circ$, $[\alpha]_D^{25} -131.6^\circ$ (EtOH). Found: C, 65.78; H, 7.42; N, 9.08. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{33}\text{N}_3\text{O}_5$ requires C, 65.91; H, 7.30; N,

washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4), and concentrated to give venenatine (1) (identified by m.m.p., co-tlc and superimposable ir with authentic sample), m.p. 123-26° (dec); yield 4.5 mg (100%). TLC of the CHCl_3 extract showed the absence of any alstovenine (5).

The ring closure reaction of 2b was carried out employing the above reaction conditions and work-up procedure. This reaction afforded a quantitative yield of alstovenine (5) (identified by m.m.p., co-tlc and superimposable ir with authentic sample). The reaction mixture showed the absence of any venenatine (1) on tlc.

Preparation of 3: Pb(OAc)₄ method: $\text{Pb}(\text{OAc})_4$ (49 mg; 0.11 mmole) was added to a solution of 2a and 2b (50 mg; 0.11 mmole) (crude reaction mixture obtained in first step without separation). The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 10 hr and filtered. The filtrate was diluted with water (20 ml), made alkaline with ammonia at 0° and then extracted with CH_2Cl_2 (50 ml $\times$ 4); the CH_2Cl_2 extract was dried (Na_2SO_4) and concentrated. The 3-keto-3,4-seco-cyanamide derivative (3) was isolated in very low yield (ca 5 mg; ca 10%) by ptlc of the concentrate on silica gel plates using 10% MeOH-EtOAc as the solvent system.

t-BuOCl method: A mixture of 2a and 2b (455 mg; 1 mmole) dissolved in 25 ml of CH_2Cl_2 was kept at 0° in an ice-salt bath. An equimolar amount of t-BuOCl (110 mg; 1 mmole) in 25 ml of CCl_4 was added to the reaction mixture over a period of 1 hr with stirring. After addition was complete the solution was stirred for 30 min with no external cooling. The yellow solution was washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and concentrated under reduced pressure to give a viscous deep brown mass. This mass was dissolved in 1% glacial AcOH in 70% MeOH- H_2O , heated at refluxing temperature under nitrogen atmosphere for 3 hr. The methanol was removed from the reaction mixture under reduced pressure and the product was isolated following the usual procedure. The crude product on chromatography over alumina yielded 3 from the C_6H_6 -EtOAc (1 : 1) eluates in colourless needles, $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{27}\text{N}_3\text{O}_5$, m.p. 260-62°(dec) (yield 361 mg; 85%), $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 261.2^\circ$ (EtOH). Found: C, 64.73; H, 6.54; N, 9.72. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{27}\text{N}_3\text{O}_5$ requires C, 64.93; H, 6.40; N, 9.88%. MS [m/e (%)] : 425 (M^+ , 100), 406(15), 397(18), 396(18), 382(10), 213(15), 207(22), 202(15), 200(10), 199(15), 198(10), 188(10), 187(10), 186(15), 174(40), 173(95), 172(15), 160(30), 144(15), 130(25), 77(10). IR ν_{max} cm^{-1} : 3480, 3340 (-NH- and -OH); 2220 (-C $\equiv$ N); 1730 (ester $\text{C}=\text{O}$); 1710 (α,β -unsaturated $\text{C}=\text{O}$); 1115, 990, 790, 745 (1,2,3-trisubstituted phenyl nucleus). UV (EtOH) λ_{max} : 311, 249 and 206 nm (log ϵ : 2.93, 3.08 and 3.26). 80 MHz ^1H -nmr (CDCl_3) δ : 3.69 and 3.81 (3H, s each; 9-OCH₃ and -CO₂CH₃); 4.11 (1H, m; C-17-H); 6.33 (1H, d of d, $J_o = 6.7$ Hz, $J_m = 1.2$ Hz; C-10-H); 6.83 (1H, d of d, $J_o =$

7.7 Hz, $J_m = 1.2$ Hz; C-12-H); 7.04 (1H, d, $J = 7.2$ Hz; C-11-H); 9.03 (1H, br s, disappeared on deuteration; indole -NH-).

Preparation of 4: Compound 3 (100 mg; 0.22 mmole) was dissolved in 5% H_2O -AcOH (25 ml). Ammonium acetate (85 mg; 1.10 mmole) was added and the reaction mixture was heated at 70° under nitrogen atmosphere for 8 hr. After the usual work-up the product on chromatography over alumina column yielded the decyano derivative, 4, from the EtOAc-MeOH (9 : 1) eluates as an amorphous powder, $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_2\text{O}_5$, (yield : 10 mg; 10%). Found: C, 65.04; H, 6.91; N, 7.15. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_2\text{O}_5$ requires C, 65.27; H, 6.78; N, 7.25%. MS [m/e (%)] : 386 (M^+ , 5), 385(25), 384(100), 383(75), 382(60), 381(10), 380(8), 378(5), 372(5), 360(8), 353(5), 324(5), 323(10), 318(8), 252(5), 251(8), 250(5), 216(12), 214(12), 198(5), 105(8). IR ν_{max} cm^{-1} : 3400-3200 (-NH- and -OH); 1730 (acid $\text{C}=\text{O}$); 1700 (α,β -unsaturated $\text{C}=\text{O}$); 1170, 1155, 1110, 790 and 750 (1,2,3-trisubstituted phenyl nucleus).

Preparation of 6a and 6b: Rhazine (6) (176 mg; 0.5 mmole) was treated with cyanogen bromide (212 mg, 2 mmole) under identical conditions employed for the preparation of 2a and 2b, using the same molar proportions. A similar work-up of the reaction mixture gave 6a (R_f 0.44) and 6b (R_f 0.48), which were separated by preparative tlc on silica gel chromatoplates using benzene : ethylacetate (1 : 1) as the developing system. Overall isolated yield 85% (6a 115 mg, 55%; 6b 64 mg, 30%). 6a was isolated as an yellow powder, $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{29}\text{N}_3\text{O}_6$, m.p. 128-131° [$\alpha]_D^{25} + 30.1^\circ$ (EtOH). Found: C, 68.21; H, 7.06; N, 9.78. $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{29}\text{N}_3\text{O}_6$ requires C, 68.07; H, 6.90; N, 9.92%. MS [m/e (%)] : 423 (M^+ , 50), 393(10), 377(5), 364(5), 318(10), 205(15), 200(20), 193(15), 191(30), 188(10), 174(50), 157(20), 156(100), 133(5), 130(60). IR ν_{max} cm^{-1} : 3400 (-NH- and -OH); 2200 (-CN); 1710 (ester $\text{C}=\text{O}$); 1150, 1050

(-C-O, stretching); 1050, 735 (1,2-disubstituted phenyl nucleus). UV (EtOH) λ_{max} : 226 and 285 nm (log ϵ : 4.38 and 3.82). 80 MHz ^1H -nmr (CDCl_3) δ : 1.13 (3H, t, $J = 7.5$ Hz; -OCH₂CH₃); 1.65 (3H, d with fine splitting, $J = 7.0$ Hz; $\text{C}=\text{CH}-\text{CH}_3$); 2.58 (3H, s; CO₂CH₃); 4.16 (2H, q, $J = 7.5$ Hz; -OCH₂CH₃); 4.82 (1H, d of d, $J_1 = 11.0$ Hz, $J_2 = 5.0$ Hz; C-3-H); 5.42 (1H, q, $J = 7.0$ Hz; $\text{C}=\text{CH}-\text{CH}_3$); 7.55 - 7.01 (4H, m; aromatic protons); 8.04 (1H, br s, disappeared on deuteration; indole -NH-).

6b was isolated as an yellowish powder, $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{29}\text{N}_3\text{O}_6$, m.p. 133-35°, [$\alpha]_D^{25} + 46.1^\circ$ (EtOH). Found: C, 68.26; H, 7.01; N, 9.82. $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{29}\text{N}_3\text{O}_6$ requires C, 68.07; H, 6.90; N, 9.92%. MS [m/e (%)] : 423 (M^+ , 8), 393(8), 377(5), 364(5), 318(5), 205(15), 200(70), 193(18), 191(72), 188(15), 174(20), 157(20),

156(100), 133(15), 130(70). IR ν_{max} cm^{-1} : 3400
 (-OH and -NH-); 2215 (CN); 1725 (ester $>C=O$);

1160, 1075 ($-C-O$ stretching); 1075, 745(1,2-disubstituted phenyl nucleus). UV (EtOH) λ_{max} : 226, 283 and 291 nm ($\log \epsilon$: 4.37, 3.77 and 3.72). 80 MHz 1H -nmr ($CDCl_3$) δ : 1.17 (3H, t, $J=7.7$ Hz; OCH_2-CH_3); 1.64 (3H, d of d, $J_1=6.6$ Hz, $J_2=1.5$ Hz; $>C=CH-CH_3$); 2.34 (3H, s; $-CO_2CH_3$); 4.30 (2H, q, $J=7.7$ Hz; $-OCH_2-CH_3$); 4.61 (1H, d of d, $J_1=11.0$ Hz, $J_2=2.5$ Hz; C-3-H); 5.59 (1H, q, $J=6.6$ Hz; $>C=CH-CH_3$); 7.45-6.94 (4H, m; aromatic protons); 8.22 (1H, br s, disappeared on deuteration; indole -NH-).

Ring closure reactions of 6a and 6b: The ring closure reactions of 6a and 6b were studied with glacial AcOH under the same conditions as used in the case of 2a and 2b. TLC analysis of the reaction products showed the presence of complex mixtures including substantial amounts of unreacted 6a and 6b.

Preparation of 7: A mixture of 6a and 6b (50 mg; 0.12 mmole) (crude mixture of products from previous reaction) was dissolved in 10 ml of CH_2Cl_2 and was kept in an ice-salt bath. Equimolar amount of *t*-BuOCl (13.2 mg; 0.12 mmole) in 10 ml of CCl_4 was added to the reaction mixture over a period of 1 hr. After addition was complete the solution was stirred for 30 min with no external cooling. The yellow solution was washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and concentrated under reduced pressure to give a viscous deep brown mass. This mass was then dissolved in 1% glacial AcOH in 70% MeOH- H_2O , heated at refluxing temperature under nitrogen atmosphere for 3 hr. The methanol was removed from the reaction mixture under reduced pressure and the product was isolated following the usual procedure. The resulting product on preparative tlc on silica gel chromatoplates using benzene-ethyl acetate (1 : 1) as the developing system afforded 7 as a yellow amorphous solid, $C_{22}H_{23}N_3O_4$ (M^+ 393) (yield : 10 mg; ca 22%). Found :

C, 66.9; H, 5.9; N, 10.5. $C_{22}H_{23}N_3O_4$ requires C, 67.2; H, 5.8; N, 10.7%. IR ν_{max} cm^{-1} : 3460-3260 (-NH- and -OH); 2190 (-CN); 1730 (ester $>C=O$); 1705 (α,β -unsaturated $>C=O$); 1150, 1060

($-C-O$ stretching); 1060, 750 (1,2-disubstituted phenyl nucleus). UV (EtOH) λ_{max} : 315, 238 and 207 nm. 80 MHz 1H -nmr ($CDCl_3$) δ : 1.74 (3H, d of d, $J_1=6.8$ Hz, $J_2=1.3$ Hz; $>C=CH-CH_3$); 3.73 (3H, s; CO_2CH_3); 5.64 (1H, q, $J=6.6$ Hz; $>C=CH-CH_3$); 7.04-7.35 (3H, m; 3 aromatic protons); 7.66-7.76 (1H, m; one aromatic proton); 9.20 (1H, br s, disappeared on deuteration; indole -NH-).

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